

Mengatasi *Mathematics Anxiety* Siswa Menggunakan *Cooperative Learning* Teknik *Two Stay Two Stray* Di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Tarbiyah Islamiyah Kota Jambi

Afriana Santosa

(Lecturer at Jarinabi Islamic College)

Abstract: This thesis aims to get the data, test, prove and determine about the influence of the use of cooperative learning technique of two stay two stray in dealing with math anxiety students at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Tarbiyah Islamiyah City of Jambi. This study is a quantitative research by using *true experimental – pretest posttest control group*. The samples are 37 students from class VII, by using *simple random sampling* technique, then divided into two classes, the control class and the experimental class. Data are collected by using questionnaire in the form of a Likert scale to find out students' math anxiety scores and be analyzed by *Independent Sample t test* and *Paired sample t test*. Based on the results of statistical analysis before treatment in the experimental class and the control class was obtained $\text{Sig. (2-tailed)} = 0,825 > 0,05$ and after treatment was obtained $\text{Sig. (2-tailed)} = 0,000 < 0,05$ meaning, there is a more significant positive direct effect between the cooperative learning with two stay two stray technique in dealing with students' Mathematics Anxiety. The study results are expected to be able to give useful and positive feedback to the teachers in order to implement learning activities which are fun, enjoyable and relaxing. This is needed in order to overcome and minimize the student anxiety and stress in studying math by applying cooperative learning two stay two stray technique.

Keywords: *Mathematics Anxiety* and *Cooperative Learning with Two Stay Two Stray Technique*

Introduction

Anxiety arises starting with a dislike of mathematics, then the idea arises that mathematics is difficult, fear so that anxiety arises in students when learning takes place. This is because anxiety can arise in each individual at different levels. Anxiety can be interpreted as something that is not calm, worried and afraid of something that is unclear or unknown. Craig (Elliot et al., 1996) said that math anxiety can simply be interpreted as a form of anxiety specifically towards mathematics subjects that are usually experienced by students at school. The reality shows that student anxiety towards mathematics is not only experienced by students who have low abilities in mathematics, students who have high abilities also feel anxiety. Basically, anxiety at low and moderate levels has a positive effect on students' learning performance, one of which is to increase learning motivation, while student anxiety at high levels can interfere with and worsen students' learning behavior. According to Nawangsari in Wicaksono and Saufi (2013, p.2) anxiety is an unpleasant condition including fear, tension, worry, confusion, dislike which is subjective and arises because of feelings of insecurity about the dangers that are suspected to occur. From the definition above, it can be said that mathematical anxiety is a form of a person's feelings, either in the form of feelings of fear, tension or anxiety in facing mathematical problems or in carrying out mathematical learning with various forms of symptoms that caused. Various external factors from the environment around

students also influence students' math anxiety. According to Crow and Crow in Handayani (2016, p.27), anxiety is an unpleasant condition experienced by individuals that can affect their physical condition. In line with what Crow and Crow stated, according to Soehardjono in Handayani (2016, p.27), anxiety is a manifestation of symptoms or physiological disorders such as: trembling, sweating, nausea, headaches, frequent urination, palpitations (fluttering or pounding). Emotional symptoms in the form of anxiety will arise from unpleasant conditions so that they can interfere with the physical condition of the individual.

Anxiety can occur at any time and is caused by anything that threatens. Anxiety can be caused by external dangers, as well as internal dangers, and in general, these threats are vague (not clear). Internal dangers arise when there is something that cannot be accepted, such as thoughts, feelings, desires and urges.

Denhere's research in Rifin Anditya and Budi Murtiyasa (2016, p.4) states that there are many factors that can cause mathematics anxiety, including:

- a) Unconducive classroom conditions
- b) National Mathematics Examination
- c) Weak teacher ability in delivering the subject matter being studied and the application of less varied learning models
- d) Mathematics has many formulas
- e) Expectations from families to get good grades
- f) Students cannot solve math problems.

The selection of learning models plays an important role in minimizing students' mathematical anxiety. In reality, learning methods are still lacking in variety and often seem to use traditional methods (conventional models) where information occurs and comes from one direction. Of course, this adds to students' boredom and lack of interest in learning mathematics.

According to Professor Freedman, there are 10 ways to overcome math anxiety (Ten Ways to Reduce Math Anxiety), namely:

- a) Overcome (avoid) negative talk
- b) Ask Questions
- c) Consider foreign language math – it must be practiced
- d) Don't rely on memorization to learn math
- e) Read the Math text well
- f) Learn math according to your style
- g) Be relaxed and comfortable when learning math

Develop responsibility for your own success and failure (Paulus Roy Saputra 2014, p.8)

Based on this theory, a person's anxiety towards mathematics is caused by several things, negative thinking and speaking, lack of courage to ask questions, still often relying on memorization, and not relaxing so far are some of the causes of students experiencing anxiety in learning mathematics, one of the alternatives that can be chosen is the cooperative learning model because in this learning students are given the opportunity to be active, communicative and emphasize responsibility for themselves and their groups with a relaxed and comfortable learning atmosphere.

Woodgard (Ahmad Zulfikar, 2013: 52) Overcoming math anxiety can use cooperative learning, this is intended to help students understand that their friends are also facing the same problems. In cooperative learning, positive interactions and dependencies will be created between students and a pleasant atmosphere during learning so that students do not feel bored and anxious during learning.

As previously mentioned, that in cooperative learning will create a pleasant atmosphere so that it can reduce feelings of anxiety in students. In cooperative learning there are various types, one of which is cooperative learning with the two stay two stray technique.

According to Syarifuddin Nurdin and Adriantoni (2016, p.182) Cooperative learning is active learning that emphasizes student activities together in groups and not individually. Students in groups develop their life skills such as finding and solving problems, decision making, logical thinking, communicating effectively and working together. Cooperative learning is learning that emphasizes activities together from finding problems to solving problems done together. The steps in implementing mathematics learning with the two stay two stray technique are as follows:

1. Students are divided into several groups, each group consisting of four people.
2. After being divided into groups, the teacher gives directions that each individual has the same tasks and responsibilities in the group.
3. The teacher provides material or teaching materials to students that will be discussed in groups, and explains the rules for group learning that will be implemented.
4. After finishing, the teacher orders two people from each group to visit other groups.
5. Members who remain in the group are given the task of conveying the results of their work and information to their guests.
6. After finishing, each guest returns to their group, and reports their findings from other groups.
7. The group matches and discusses the results of their work.
8. The teacher and students together discuss the tasks that have been discussed.

Looking at the steps in implementing mathematics learning with the two stay two stray technique, students can get many benefits, including students in their group get information at once from two different groups and students have many opportunities to communicate by expressing opinions by stating mathematical ideas to other students, so that it can improve students' skills in learning with a happy and pleasant, friendly, relaxed but serious state and make it easier for them to remember and understand the lesson.

Therefore, based on the explanation, there is an assumption that the cooperative learning model of the two stay two stray technique can overcome students' mathematical anxiety at the Madrasah Tsanawiyah Tarbiyah Islamiyah in Jambi City.

As for the benchmark or guideline that students experience mathematical anxiety, according to Cooke in Ahmad Zulfikar (2011, p. 48) provides an illustration that a person's mathematical anxiety can be identified from 4 indicators, namely mathematics knowledge/understanding, somatic, cognitive, and attitude. Mathematics knowledge/understanding is related to things like the emergence of thoughts that he does not know enough about mathematics. Somatic related to changes in the individual's physical condition, for example sweating or a rapid heartbeat. Cognitive related to changes in a person's cognition when dealing with mathematics, such as not being able to think clearly or forgetting things that they usually remember. Meanwhile, Attitude related to the attitude that arises when someone has math anxiety, for example they are not confident in doing what is asked or are reluctant to do it.

Measure to students' math anxiety in this study, researchers used a questionnaire with a Likert scale model through the dimensions of math anxiety that have been explained previously, namely the mathematics knowledge/understanding dimension with an indicator of thinking they don't know enough about mathematics. Somatic dimension with an indicator of changes in body condition when facing mathematics lessons. Cognitive dimension with an indicator of changes in a person's cognition when dealing with mathematics. And the attitude dimension with an indicator of attitudes that arise when someone has math anxiety.

In collecting data, researchers used a Likert scale model, a measurement scale with this type will get answers always, often, rarely and never. The statements given are divided into two items, namely positive items and negative items.

Table 1.1 Scoring Criteria for the Student Mathematics Anxiety Data Collection Instrument Alternative Answers Positive Items Negative Items

Alternatif Jawaban	SL	S	J	TP
Item (+)	4	3	2	1
Item (-)	1	2	3	4

Method

This study uses the "Pretest-Posttest Control Group Design" design. The independent variable (Independent) is cooperative learning using the two stay two stray technique while the dependent variable is students' mathematical anxiety. The subjects of this study (Population) are all students of Mts Tarbiyah Islamiyah Jambi City and the sample of this study is students in class VII A and VII B, from the two classes, class VII A becomes the experimental class (treatment) in the form of a cooperative learning model using the two stay two stray technique while class VII B becomes the control class. This research was conducted in the even semester of the 2024/2025 academic year starting from February to May 2025, with a total of 37 students.

The research instrument used in this study used a non-test data collection tool in the form of a Likert scale questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed before and after treatment, for the questionnaire distributed before treatment there were 3 items that did not meet the validity requirements, so the number of statements used for data analysis was 17 statements. While the questionnaire distributed after treatment had 8 items that did not meet the validity requirements, the number of statements used was 12 statements. After the empirical validity test was carried out, the reliability test of the data instrument was carried out and the reliability value of the questionnaire distributed before treatment was 0.81, including high reliability criteria. While for the questionnaire distributed after treatment, the reliability value was 0.70, including moderate (sufficient) reliability criteria. The data obtained from the questionnaire were analyzed using mean difference statistics, namely the independent samples t test and paired samples t test (Riduwan and Sunarto, 2012) and Sudijono, (2011). The statistical hypothesis tested with the statistics of the difference between two means is as follows:

The first statistical hypothesis of the experimental class before and after treatment (Paired samples t test) is:

H_0 : If the Sig value (2-tailed) > 0.05 , then there is no significant direct effect between the cooperative learning model and the two stay two stray technique in overcoming students' math anxiety.

H_a : If the Sig value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , then there is a significant direct effect between the cooperative learning model and the two stay two stray technique in overcoming students' math anxiety.

The second statistical hypothesis of the Control Class before and after treatment (Paired samples t test) is:

H_0 : If the Sig value (2-tailed) > 0.05 , then there is no significant direct effect between the cooperative learning model and the two stay two stray technique in overcoming students' math anxiety.

H_a : If the Sig value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , then there is a significant direct effect between the cooperative learning model and the two stay two stray technique in overcoming students' math anxiety.

The third statistical hypothesis (Independent samples t test) is:

H_0 : If the Sig value (2-tailed) > 0.05 , then there is no significant difference between the average scores of students' math anxiety in the experimental and control classes before learning.

H_a : If the Sig value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , then there is a significant difference between the average scores of students' math anxiety in the experimental and control classes before learning.

The fourth statistical hypothesis (Independent samples t test) is:

H_0 : If the Sig value (2-tailed) > 0.05 , then there is no significant difference between the average scores of students' math anxiety in the experimental and control classes after learning.

H_a : If the Sig value (2-tailed) < 0.05 , then there is a significant difference between the average scores of students' math anxiety in the experimental and control classes after learning.

Research Results and Discussion

All research data were analyzed using the independent samples t-test difference statistic and the paired samples t-test difference statistic, which are described in detail below.

Research Results

1. Differences in Mathematics Anxiety Before and After Treatment in the Experimental Class (Pretest – Post test)

The average score of students' mathematics anxiety before treatment was 47.28 and the average after treatment was 25.22, experiencing an average decrease after treatment of 22.06. Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that the P-Value = 0.000 < 0.05 , so it can be concluded that the average score of students' mathematics anxiety in the experimental class before and after treatment has a significantly different average score.

2. Differences in Mathematics Anxiety Before and After Learning in the Control Class (Pretest - Posttest)

The average score of students' mathematics anxiety before learning was 47.79 and the average after learning was 33.53, experiencing an average decrease after learning of 14.26. Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that the P-Value = 0.000 < 0.05 , it can be concluded that the average score of students' mathematics anxiety in the control class before and after learning has a different average score, but not as significant as the experimental class.

3. Differences in Students' Mathematics Anxiety between the Control Class and the Experimental Class Before Treatment (Pretest)

Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out between the control class and the experimental class before learning, it states that there is no significant difference in the average score of students' mathematics anxiety before treatment in the experimental class (mean 47.28) and control (mean 47.79). This data defines that the average score of students' mathematics anxiety in the two classes (experimental and control) before treatment is at the same level. Then the results of the statistical analysis of the difference in the two means (independent samples t test) found a probability (p) of $0.825 > \alpha 0.05$. This fact shows that there is no significant difference in the average score of students' mathematics anxiety before treatment in the experimental and control classes.

4. Differences in Students' Mathematics Anxiety between the Control Class and the Experimental Class After Treatment (Post test)

There is a significant difference in the average score of students' mathematics anxiety after treatment in the experimental class (mean 25.22) and control (mean 33.53). This data defines that after treatment the average score of students' mathematics anxiety in the experimental class is lower than the control class. Then the results of the statistical analysis of the difference in two means (Independent samples t test) found a probability (p) of $.000 < \alpha 0.05$. This means that there is a significant difference between the average score of mathematics anxiety in the experimental class and the control class after treatment.

Discussion

1. Students' Mathematics Anxiety Level Before and After Treatment in Experimental Class and Control Class

The results of the descriptive analysis showed that there was a significant change in the level of students' mathematics anxiety in the experimental class before and after treatment, while in the control class before and after learning there was also a change, but the change was not significant.

The cooperative learning model applied can be used as an alternative in overcoming students' mathematics anxiety. This is in line with the research conducted by Annisa Safitri (2016, p. 96) stating that the average score of students' mathematics anxiety after being given treatment in the form of a game method (post-test) was lower than the average score of mathematics anxiety before being given treatment (pre-test).

This research is also in line with the research conducted by Erick Santoso (2017, p. 40), the results of the study concluded that the mathematics anxiety score decreased after being given treatment in the form of a logic game.

The results of this study did not have a significant difference with the results of the study by Mutodi and Hlanganipani Ngirande in Rifin Anditya (2016, p.10) where the results of the study concluded that very few students were free from mathematical anxiety

problems, and in general the level of mathematical anxiety of the majority of students was at a moderate level.

2. Differences in Students' Mathematics Anxiety Before and After Treatment in the Experimental Class

The results of the analysis showed that there was a difference in the average score of mathematical anxiety before and after cooperative learning using the two stay two stray technique. This is in line with previous empirical research and findings by Ahmad Zulfikar (2013, p. 52) stating that the cooperative model can be used to overcome students' mathematical anxiety, this is intended to help students that their friends are also facing the same problem. In cooperative learning, positive interactions and dependencies will be created between students and a pleasant atmosphere during learning so that students do not feel bored and anxious during learning.

3. Differences in Students' Mathematics Anxiety Between the Control Class and the Experimental Class

The results of the analysis showed that there was a difference in the average score of mathematical anxiety between the control class and the experimental class, where the experimental class had a lower average score of mathematical anxiety, based on these results it is assumed that the experimental class (cooperative learning technique two stay two stray) can overcome students' mathematical anxiety than the control class (direct learning).

The results of this study are in line with the findings of previous studies (Aulia 2013), which stated that cooperative learning is effective in reducing students' mathematical anxiety when compared to conventional learning. In addition, there is a negative correlation between mathematical anxiety and students' mathematical understanding abilities. With the correlation level in the CRH class being classified as high and the class with conventional learning being classified as very high.

This is also in line with Anita's research (2011) in her research she found that students' mathematical abilities are influenced by the mathematical anxiety in the students.

Conclusion

It is concluded that, first, the level of mathematical anxiety in the experimental class and the control class experienced changes, but when viewed from the average score of mathematical anxiety obtained, the experimental class showed a more significant positive direct influence in overcoming students' mathematical anxiety.

Second, the average score of students' mathematical anxiety in the experimental class decreased significantly through the Cooperative Learning Technique Two Stay Two Stray learning process.

Third, students' mathematical anxiety in the control class and the experimental class before the treatment had the same average. After the implementation of the cooperative learning technique two stay two stray in the experimental class, there was a difference in the average score of students' mathematical anxiety. It was concluded that the cause of the difference in the average score of mathematical anxiety was the treatment given in the experimental class. In connection with the findings of this theory, it is valuable input for teachers and prospective teachers of mathematics education in an effort to overcome or minimize students' mathematical anxiety.

Bibliography

- Anditya, Rifin. (2016). *Factors Causing Mathematics Anxiety*. Surakarta. Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta
- Arikunto, S. (2010). *Research Procedure of a Practical Approach*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Dzulfikar, Ahmad. (2013) *Literature study: Cooperative Learning in Overcoming Mathematics Anxiety and Developing Students' Mathematical Self-Efficacy*. ISBN: 978-979-16353-9-4. Yogyakarta: National Seminar on Mathematics and Mathematics Education, FMIPA UNY.
- Dzulfikar Ahmad (2016). *Mathematics Anxiety in Prospective Mathematics Teacher Students*. *Journal of Mathematics and Mathematics Education* Volume. 1 No. 1: Darul `Ulum Islamic Boarding School University.
- Eka Indiyani, Novita & Anita Listiara. (2006). *Effectiveness of Mutual Cooperation Learning Method (Cooperative Learning) to Reduce Students' Anxiety in Facing Mathematics Lessons*. *Journal of Psychology, Diponegoro University* Vol. 3 No. 1
- Fajar Susetyo, Yuli. (2012) *The Secret to Success in Becoming a Student Motivator*. Yogyakarta: Pinus Book Publisher.
- Gazali, M. (2015). *The Influence of Self-Efficacy and Mathematics Anxiety on Students' Critical Thinking Skills in Mathematics Subjects in Junior High Schools in Ciledug District*. Thesis: Postgraduate School Education Research and Evaluation Study Program. UHAMKA.
- Riduwan, (2013). *Introduction to Statistics for Educational Research*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Roy Saputra, Paulus. (2014). *Mathematics Anxiety and How to Reduce It*. *Pythagoras Journal* Vol.3(2):75-84. ISSN 2301-5314. Riau: Mathematics Education Study Program, FKIP UNRI, Batam Islands.
- Rudiansyah, et al.(2016). *Teachers' Efforts in Overcoming Students' Anxiety in Facing Tests (Learning Achievement) of Students at Smp Negeri 3 Banda Aceh*. *Unsyiah Scientific Journal* Volume 1, Number 1:96-109.

- Safitri, Anissa. (2016). The Effect of Game Methods on Mathematics Anxiety in Learning Mathematics of Grade IV Students of SDN Pondok Ranji. Jakarta: PGMI Study Program UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta
- Santoso, Erik. (2017). Overcoming Math Anxiety by Playing Logic Games. THEOREMS Journal (The Original Research of Mathematics). Vol.1 No.2, 31-41. Bekasi: Lecturer of Mathematics Study Program, Majalengka University.
- Sudijono, A. (2014). Introduction to Educational Statistics. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sugiyono. (2017). Educational Research Methods Qualitative, Quantitative and R & D Approaches. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2016). Educational Research Methods Qualitative, Quantitative and R & D Approaches. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sudjana, Nana. (2009). Basics of Teaching and Learning Process. Bandung: Sinar Baru Algesindo
- Sudjana, Nana. (2005). Statistical Methods. Bandung: PT. Tarsito Bandung
- Suhana, C. (2014). Learning Strategy Concept. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
- Syarifuddin Nurdin and Adriantoni. (2016). Curriculum and Learning. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Wicaksono, Arif Budi and M. Saufi. (2013) Managing Students' Mathematics Anxiety in Mathematics Learning. ISBN: 978-979-16353-9-4 Yogyakarta: National Seminar on Mathematics and Mathematics Education FMIPA UNY.